

22NRM06 ADMIT

Deliverable D8

Evidence of contributions to new or improved international guides, recommendations and standards with a specific focus on the following guides and committees: IEC TC38, IEC TC38/WG47, IEC TC38/IEEE IMS TC39 JWG55. Examples of early uptake of project outputs by end-users.

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**METROLOGY
PARTNERSHIP**

EURAMET

Glossary

Acronym	Meaning
AC	Alternating Current
CT	Current Transformer
DAQ	Data Acquisition System
DC	Direct Current
DUT	Device Under Test
EMC	Electromagnetic Compatibility
FFT	Fast Fourier Transform
FSM	Frequency Sweep Method
HF	High Frequency
HFD	High-Frequency Distortion
HFA	High Frequency Amplifier
HFRD	High Frequency Reference Device
HFVT	High-Frequency Voltage Transformer
HV	High Voltage
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IT	Instrument Transformer
LPIT	Low-Power Instrument Transformer
LV	Low Voltage
LVD	Low Voltage Divider
LFA	Low Frequency Amplifier
LFRD	Low Frequency Reference Device
MTM	Multi-Tone Method
MV	Medium Voltage
NMI	National Metrology Institute
PFG	Power Frequency Generator
PI	Performance Index
PLL	Phase Locked Loop
PQ	Power Quality
PXI	PCI eXtensions for Instrumentation
RC	Resistive-Capacitive
RCVD	Resistive-Capacitive Voltage Divider
RMS	Root Mean Square
SF	Scale Factor
SFS	Sinusoidal Frequency Sweep
TVE	Total Vector Error
TFRD	Total Frequency Response Deviation
TUR	Test Uncertainty Ratio
UD	Universal Divider
VT	Voltage Transformer
WB	Wideband Accuracy Class

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1 Summary

The ADMIT project addressed the characterization of instrument transformers operating in medium-voltage AC and DC networks in the extended frequency range from the power frequency up to 150 kHz. The project responded to the growing impact of converter-based technologies, renewable generation, EV charging infrastructure and power-electronic devices, which introduce harmonic and supraharmonic disturbances not fully covered by existing standards.

This deliverable summarizes the main outcomes of Deliverables D1–D7 and documents their contribution to future standardization activities within IEC/CENELEC TC38. The work covered the characterization of real disturbances in medium-voltage networks, the definition of accuracy and uncertainty requirements for instrument transformers, the development of representative test waveforms, the realization of voltage and current generation systems, and the validation of traceable reference measurement systems for both voltage and current quantities.

The project demonstrated that accurate characterization of instrument transformers up to 150 kHz is technically feasible, provided that dedicated generation systems, reference measurement infrastructures and uncertainty evaluation procedures are employed. The work also highlighted the importance of realistic multitone and transient testing, identified practical limitations associated with low-level signal measurements, and proposed performance indexes and calibration methodologies suitable for wideband characterization.

The resulting recommendations have been consolidated in Deliverable D7 and communicated to IEC/CENELEC TC38 to support future developments of the IEC 61869 family of standards. Collectively, the project outcomes provide a technical and metrological basis for future wideband instrument-transformer calibration services and for the harmonized assessment of instrument-transformer performance in the supraharmonic range.

2 Introduction

The increasing deployment of renewable-energy generation, electric vehicle charging infrastructure and power-electronic converters is transforming the electrical grid and introducing disturbances extending far beyond the traditional harmonic range. As a result, instrument transformers used for measurement, protection and power-quality applications are increasingly required to operate accurately in the frequency range between 9 kHz and 150 kHz, commonly referred to as the supraharmonic range.

Although the latest edition of IEC 61869 introduced wideband accuracy classes extending up to 500 kHz, practical methodologies for the characterization, calibration and conformity assessment of instrument transformers above the power frequency remain largely undefined. In particular, significant gaps exist regarding representative test waveforms, generation systems, reference measurement infrastructures, uncertainty evaluation procedures and performance indexes suitable for wideband operation.

The ADMIT project was initiated to address these challenges and to provide the metrological foundations necessary for future standardization activities. Through a combination of literature reviews, field measurements, numerical simulations, development of generation systems, validation of reference measurement systems and uncertainty analysis, the project established a comprehensive framework for the characterization of instrument transformers up to 150 kHz.

This deliverable provides a synthesis of the main outcomes of Deliverables D1–D7 and highlights their relevance for future standardization work within IEC/CENELEC TC38. The document summarizes the technical evidence generated by the project, the practical solutions developed for voltage and current generation and measurement, and the recommendations formulated to support future revisions of the IEC 61869 family of standards.

3 Deliverable D1

3.1 Introduction

Deliverable D1 established the technical basis for the characterization of Instrument Transformers (ITs), including Voltage Transformers (VTs) and Current Transformers (CTs), intended for use in AC and DC medium-voltage networks up to 36 kV and in the extended frequency range up to 150 kHz. The work addressed the growing relevance of disturbances above the traditional harmonic range and focused on identifying realistic operating conditions, defining suitable test waveforms, assessing future measurement needs, and deriving performance and uncertainty requirements for both ITs and the measuring systems connected to them. The conclusions were supported by a combination of literature and standards reviews, numerical simulations of realistic power systems, dedicated measurement campaigns in medium-voltage networks, and metrological analyses aimed at future standardization.

3.2 High-Frequency Distortion and Supraharmonics

The analysis confirmed that High-Frequency Distortion (HFD), often referred to as supraharmonics, has become an increasingly important power-quality issue due to the widespread deployment of power-electronic equipment such as photovoltaic systems, EV charging infrastructure, wind-power converters, LED lighting systems, and power-line communication devices. These disturbances typically occur above 9 kHz and can extend well beyond 100 kHz, reaching 150 kHz and beyond in some cases [\[2\]](#).

The review highlighted a range of documented impacts, including increased losses, accelerated ageing of insulation systems, degradation of cable terminations, interference with communication systems, and malfunctions of protection and metering equipment [\[3\]](#). Analysis of available literature showed that the most significant emissions are generally concentrated around switching frequencies in the range of 10–50 kHz, particularly around 10 kHz and 12–16 kHz, although resonance phenomena may produce significant components up to 100–150 kHz [\[4\]](#).

3.3 Standardization and Metrological Gaps

A review of the relevant standards, including IEC 61000-4-7, IEC 61000-4-30, IEC 61869, IEEE 1159 and EN 50160, confirmed that while measurement methods and disturbance classifications are available, there remains a lack of harmonized procedures for the characterization of ITs in the frequency range above the power frequency.

The publication of IEC 61869-1 Edition 2 introduced the wideband accuracy classes WB0 to WB4, extending the concept of IT accuracy up to 500 kHz [\[5\]](#). However, the standard currently does not specify how compliance with these classes should be verified. In particular, guidance is still lacking regarding test waveforms, harmonic injection methods, reference measurement systems, and uncertainty evaluation procedures. This absence of harmonized methodologies was identified as one of the principal motivations for the ADMIT project.

3.4 Measurement Methods and Uncertainty Considerations

The review of available measurement techniques showed that both time-domain and frequency-domain approaches are currently used for the assessment of supraharmonic disturbances. Time-domain methods generally offer high temporal resolution and good immunity to noise, while frequency-domain approaches provide superior spectral resolution and are more easily linked to existing power-quality methodologies [\[6\]](#).

Regardless of the selected method, the study demonstrated that measurement uncertainty is strongly influenced by the bandwidth of the sensor, the resolution of the acquisition system, the relative amplitude of the harmonic component compared with the fundamental, and the overall noise floor of the measurement chain. These factors become increasingly critical as frequency increases and harmonic amplitudes decrease.

3.5 Numerical Simulations of MV/LV Networks

To complement the literature review, extensive simulations of realistic MV/LV networks were performed. The models included MV/LV transformers, converter-based sources, distributed cable capacitances, varying loading conditions, and transformer parasitic capacitances.

The simulations showed that resonance phenomena can occur throughout the frequency range of interest, typically between 25 kHz and 100 kHz, and that transformer parasitic capacitances have a strong influence on

the transfer of disturbances between voltage levels. Depending on network configuration, transfer ratios between LV and MV systems may vary from a few percent up to values approaching unity, while local resonances may even result in amplification of certain frequency components.

Although the simulated disturbance levels were generally small, typically in the range of tens to hundreds of millivolts on the MV side and a few milliamperes to tens of milliamperes for current, the simulations confirmed that converter switching transients can excite network resonances and generate localized amplification effects. These findings highlight the need for IT characterization methods that remain valid under realistic resonant conditions.

3.6 MV Measurement Campaign

The simulation results were complemented by a long-term measurement campaign performed in a 23 kV distribution network supplying EV charging infrastructure in Milan, in collaboration with Unareti S.p.A (Fig. 1). The measurements confirmed that supraharmonic voltage levels in MV networks are generally low, typically below 30 V RMS within a 10 kHz frequency band and usually below 0.2 % of nominal voltage. The dominant emissions were concentrated below 50 kHz, while current disturbances above 20 kHz generally remained below 1 A on the LV side.

Although the overall disturbance levels were modest, the measurements also confirmed that local operating conditions and resonance effects may generate significantly higher values at specific frequencies. These observations provided an important experimental basis for defining realistic test levels and sensitivity requirements for future IT characterization procedures.

3.7 Future Measurement Needs

The analysis identified several issues that remain unresolved from both a metrological and standardization perspective. These include the absence of harmonized compatibility levels in the 9–150 kHz range, difficulties in comparing results obtained using different measurement bandwidths and detector types, the strong influence of grid impedance and resonances on measured values, and the lack of agreed reference waveforms for IT testing.

Consequently, the deliverable highlighted the need for common definitions of measurement bandwidth, aggregation procedures, disturbance profiles, and compatibility levels. Particular attention was also given to the interaction between power-quality and electromagnetic-compatibility requirements, especially regarding power-line communication systems and converter-based technologies.

3.8 Performance Requirements for ITs

A central outcome of D1 was the derivation of performance requirements for ITs operating up to 150 kHz. Two complementary testing approaches were considered. The first is based on frequency sweeps and single-tone injections, providing relatively low measurement uncertainty. The second relies on multitoned waveforms combining fundamental and harmonic components, offering a more realistic representation of actual operating conditions.

The analysis demonstrated that measurement uncertainty becomes the limiting factor for IT characterization at high frequency, particularly when harmonic amplitudes at the sensor output fall below approximately 1 mV or 1 mA. Under these conditions, the achievable uncertainty is increasingly determined by the performance of the measurement system rather than by the IT itself.

The study showed that, for harmonic output levels above approximately 10 mV, minimum achievable IT accuracies remain in the range of 0.15–0.45 %, depending on frequency and test method. At lower signal levels, the uncertainty increases significantly and may exceed several percent. These findings (see [Table 1 and 2](#)) provide an important basis for future discussions on the practical implementation of the IEC 61869 wideband classes.

Table 1. Recommended minimum accuracy for harmonics using the frequency sweep

Amplitude of harmonics at the output of IT	Frequency Range	Typical U_{NMI}	Minimum required IT Accuracy
>10 mV	1 kHz to 10 kHz	0.01 %	0.15 %
	10 kHz – 150 kHz	0.02 %	0.30 %
	100 kHz – 150 kHz	0.03 %	0.45 %
>1 mV	1 kHz to 10 kHz	0.06 %	0.9 %
	10 kHz – 100 kHz	0.2 %	3,0 %
	100 kHz – 150 kHz	0.3 %	4.5 %
>10 mA	1 kHz to 10 kHz	0.02 %	0.15 %
	10 kHz – 150 kHz	0.03 %	0.30 %
	100 kHz – 150 kHz	0.05 %	0.45 %
>1 mA	1 kHz to 10 kHz	0.1 %	0.9 %
	10 kHz – 100 kHz	0.2 %	3,0 %
	100 kHz – 150 kHz	0.3 %	4.5 %

Table 2. Recommended minimum accuracy for harmonics using the simplified methods

Amplitude of harmonics at the output of IT	Frequency Range	Typical U_{NMI}	Minimum required IT Accuracy
>10 mV	1 kHz to 10 kHz	0.05 %	0.75 %
	10 kHz – 100 kHz	0.1 %	1.5 %
	100 kHz – 150 kHz	0.1 %	1.5 %
>1 mV	1 kHz to 10 kHz	0.5 %	7.5 %
	10 kHz – 100 kHz	1 %	15 %
	100 kHz – 150 kHz	1.5 %	22 %
>10 mA	1 kHz to 10 kHz	0.1 %	0.75 %
	10 kHz – 100 kHz	0.2 %	1.5 %
	100 kHz – 150 kHz	0.2 %	1.5 %
>1 mA	1 kHz to 10 kHz	0.5 %	7.5 %
	10 kHz – 100 kHz	1 %	15 %
	100 kHz – 150 kHz	1.5 %	22 %

3.9 Recommended Test Levels

Based on the combined evidence from literature, simulations, and field measurements, D1 recommended testing ITs with harmonic and supraharmmonic amplitudes corresponding to a few percent of the rated quantity. For VTs, representative levels were identified as approximately 5 % of nominal voltage in the lower supraharmmonic range, decreasing to 1–3 % above 50 kHz. Similar percentages were recommended for current transformers.

For example, characterization of a 20 kV VT may require the generation of up to 1 kV of supraharmmonic content, while a 200 A CT may require approximately 10 A of superimposed high-frequency current. The study also highlighted that excessively low injection levels may compromise measurement uncertainty and that testing harmonics in isolation may not always reproduce the same behaviour observed when harmonics are superimposed on the fundamental component.

3.10 Conclusion

D1 demonstrated that supraharmonics have become a relevant aspect of modern power systems and that existing standards do not yet provide complete methodologies for the characterization of instrument transformers in the frequency range above the power frequency. The work showed that realistic testing requires waveforms that reproduce the simultaneous presence of disturbances and resonance phenomena observed in actual networks.

Both simulations and field measurements confirmed that disturbance levels are generally small but may be locally amplified by network resonances, particularly in the frequency range between 10 kHz and 100 kHz. The study further demonstrated that measurement uncertainty rapidly becomes the dominant limitation for IT characterization as frequency increases and signal levels decrease.

The deliverable therefore concluded that future standardized assessment procedures should include both simplified frequency-sweep methods and multitoned approaches, as they provide complementary information. Overall, D1 established the technical and metrological foundation for future IEC standardization activities related to wideband instrument transformers and power-quality measurements up to 150 kHz.

4 Deliverable D2

4.1 Introduction

Deliverable D2 builds on the foundations established in D1 and addresses one of the central objectives of the ADMIT project: the definition of suitable parameters, calibration procedures, uncertainty limits and performance indexes for the characterization of Instrument Transformers (ITs) operating in the frequency range up to 150 kHz. The work supports the extension of metrological traceability and power-quality assessment into the supraharmic range and provides technical input for future standardization activities within IEC/CENELEC TC38. In particular, the deliverable focuses on three closely related aspects: the definition of suitable accuracy parameters for wideband IT characterization, the development of calibration methodologies and testing procedures, and the evaluation of the associated uncertainty budgets. The outcomes of this work also formed the basis for the round-robin activities carried out in WP2 and WP3 on selected voltage and current transformers.

4.2 Standards Framework and Existing Requirements

The analysis of the existing standards framework confirmed that the IEC/EN 61869 family remains the primary reference for IT metrology. Particular attention was devoted to EN 61869-1 (2024), which introduced the concept of wideband accuracy classes extending IT characterization well beyond the traditional harmonic range and into the supraharmic domain [7]. The standard defines five frequency extensions, namely WB0, WB1, WB2, WB3 and WB4, covering frequency ranges from the 13th harmonic up to 500 kHz. These classes provide a practical mechanism for specifying transformer performance over extended frequency ranges. However, D2 highlights that the standard currently defines admissible accuracy limits without providing harmonized procedures for their verification. In particular, detailed guidance is still lacking regarding waveform generation, calibration methods, uncertainty evaluation and reference measurement systems.

The deliverable also reviews IEC 61869-6 and TR 61869-103, emphasizing that high-frequency behavior introduces additional challenges not fully addressed in existing standards. For example, capacitive loading effects become increasingly relevant at higher frequencies, particularly for Low-Power Instrument Transformers (LPITs), and can significantly influence the measured performance.

4.3 Calibration Approaches and Accuracy Assessment

A major contribution of D2 is the comparison of alternative calibration methodologies suitable for frequencies up to 150 kHz. The work confirms that modern IT characterization increasingly relies on digital acquisition systems and comparisons against reference transformers or reference sensors [8]. The analysis identifies two complementary calibration approaches. The first is the Frequency Sweep Method (FSM), in which individual sinusoidal components are injected sequentially over the frequency range of interest. This method provides a direct determination of the transfer function and generally results in lower measurement uncertainty. The second is the Multi-Tone Method (MTM), where harmonics and supraharmics are superimposed on the fundamental quantity. Although more complex to implement, this approach better reproduces actual operating conditions and allows the investigation of non-linear effects and intermodulation phenomena.

A key conclusion of the deliverable is that these methods are not necessarily equivalent. Instrument transformers may exhibit different behaviour when harmonic components are applied individually or when they are superimposed on a rated fundamental signal. Consequently, both methods should be considered complementary rather than interchangeable.

4.4 Frequency Resolution and Signal Processing

The deliverable also investigates the influence of signal-processing parameters on measurement accuracy. Existing EMC and power-quality standards typically employ resolution bandwidths between 5 Hz and 200 Hz [9]. However, for laboratory calibration of ITs, much finer frequency resolution is generally preferable because it reduces noise contributions and improves amplitude estimation accuracy. The study confirms the importance of synchronized acquisition over an integer number of fundamental cycles to minimize spectral leakage and avoid errors introduced by windowing techniques. It also highlights that frequency stability becomes increasingly critical at higher frequencies, as even small variations of the fundamental frequency can produce significant deviations when translated to harmonic orders corresponding to 150 kHz.

Consequently, the aggregation procedures commonly used for long-term grid monitoring are considered inappropriate for laboratory calibration purposes, where stable and repeatable signals are required.

4.5 Uncertainty Budget and Accuracy Requirements

D2 further develops the uncertainty analysis initiated in D1 and examines the complete calibration chain from National Metrology Institutes (NMIs) to industrial laboratories. The analysis confirms the importance of maintaining a Test Uncertainty Ratio (TUR) greater than three in order to ensure reliable conformity assessment. A major finding is that uncertainty increasingly depends on the measurement system itself rather than on the transformer under test. At high frequencies, the output signals of many ITs fall into the millivolt or milliamper range, making measurements particularly sensitive to quantization effects, noise, shunt uncertainties and acquisition-system limitations [10].

The study shows that when harmonic output amplitudes exceed approximately 10 mV or 10 mA, achievable uncertainties remain compatible with the wideband accuracy classes defined in IEC 61869. However, when signal levels approach 1 mV or 1 mA, uncertainty increases rapidly and may exceed the limits implied by the existing accuracy classes.

The analysis also highlights the limitations of commercially available instrumentation. Standard 16-bit acquisition systems are generally insufficient for reliable measurements of very low-level harmonic signals at high frequencies. Even high-performance 24-bit systems become increasingly challenged as signal amplitudes approach the microvolt range. As a result, accurate wideband characterization often requires dedicated low-noise architectures including amplification and filtering stages specifically designed for this application [11].

Table 3. Recommended minimum accuracy for harmonics using the FSM

Amplitude of harmonics at the output of IT	Frequency Range	Typical u_{NMI}	Minimum IT Accuracy
> 10 mV	1 kHz – 10 kHz	0.014 %	0.21 %
	10 kHz – 50 kHz	0.024 %	0.36 %
	50 kHz – 150 kHz	0.04 %	0.60 %
> 1 mV	1 kHz – 10 kHz	0.10 %	0.90 %
	10 kHz – 50 kHz	0.10 %	0.90 %
	50 kHz – 150 kHz	0.11 %	1.0 %
> 10 mA	1 kHz – 10 kHz	0.04 %	0.60 %
	10 kHz – 50 kHz	0.08 %	0.72 %
	50 kHz – 150 kHz	0.20 %	1.8 %
> 1 mA	1 kHz – 10 kHz	0.11 %	1.65 %
	10 kHz – 50 kHz	0.13 %	1.95 %
	50 kHz – 150 kHz	0.22 %	3.3 %

Table 4. Recommended minimum accuracy for harmonics using the MTM

Amplitude of harmonics at the output of IT	Frequency Range	Typical u_{NMI}	Minimum IT Accuracy
> 10 mV	1 kHz – 10 kHz	0.04 %	0.45 %
	10 kHz – 50 kHz	0.07 %	0.54 %
	50 kHz – 150 kHz	0.12 %	0.80 %
> 1 mV	1 kHz – 10 kHz	0.22 %	1.98 %
	10 kHz – 50 kHz	0.22 %	1.98 %
	50 kHz – 150 kHz	0.24 %	2.16 %
> 10 mA	1 kHz – 10 kHz	0.12 %	1.08 %
	10 kHz – 50 kHz	0.20 %	1.8 %
	50 kHz – 150 kHz	0.40 %	3.6 %
> 1 mA	1 kHz – 10 kHz	0.26 %	2.34 %
	10 kHz – 50 kHz	0.33 %	2.97 %
	50 kHz – 150 kHz	0.44 %	3.96 %

4.6 Performance Indexes for Wideband Characterization

The deliverable proposes a set of performance indexes intended to complement the traditional ratio and phase errors used for IT characterization. While ratio error and phase displacement remain the primary quantities, D2 introduces more synthetic indicators capable of describing transformer behaviour over a wide frequency range. These include the Frequency Response Deviation Index, the Total Frequency Response Deviation (TFRD), the Total Vector Error (TVE), and THD-based metrics adapted to harmonic and supraharmonic intervals.

Among these indicators, the TFRD is identified as particularly useful because it combines weighted frequency-dependent deviations into a single quantity representative of the overall wideband behaviour of the transformer. Similarly, THD-derived metrics provide compact indicators of performance over selected frequency intervals, although they mainly reflect amplitude behaviour and do not capture phase distortions [12]. The deliverable also extends the analysis into the time domain by introducing waveform-based indicators such as Euclidean error norms, maximum instantaneous error, integral absolute error and correlation-based metrics. Particular attention is devoted to time alignment, as propagation delays introduced by the transformer may otherwise appear as artificial amplitude errors.

4.7 Representative Test Waveforms

A substantial part of D2 is devoted to the definition of representative test waveforms for wideband IT characterization. Frequency-domain testing is based on combinations of DC or AC fundamentals, harmonics and supraharmonics. Typical switching frequencies observed in converter-based equipment are concentrated between approximately 4 kHz and 20 kHz, with particularly frequent occurrences around 8 kHz, 10 kHz and 16 kHz. Harmonics of these switching frequencies may remain significant up to approximately 50 kHz [3].

The recommended test amplitudes are derived from the literature review and measurement campaigns performed within the project. For low-voltage applications, harmonic amplitudes between approximately 0.5 % and 2 % of nominal values are considered representative. For medium-voltage systems, lower amplitudes appear more realistic, typically up to 1 % below 10 kHz, between 0.2 % and 0.5 % from 10 kHz to 50 kHz, and approximately 0.1 % above 50 kHz.

The report also emphasizes the importance of multitone testing. When several supraharmonic components are simultaneously present, their instantaneous superposition may generate significantly larger peak values than those associated with individual components. This effect must be considered when designing generation systems and amplifiers. In addition to frequency-domain waveforms, D2 discusses time-domain signals such as tapered sinc waveforms and transient waveforms derived from EMC testing practices. In particular, sinc

waveforms are considered attractive because of their nearly rectangular spectrum, enabling simultaneous excitation of a broad frequency range [\[13\]](#).

4.8 Round-Robin Activities

The deliverable defines the waveform set adopted for the WP2 and WP3 round-robin activities. These tests included pure power-frequency excitation, individual supraharmonic tones, multitone conditions, amplitude variation tests and optional sinc-based transient signals. The selected waveforms were intended to reproduce both controlled laboratory conditions and realistic disturbance scenarios, while providing a common basis for comparing the performance of different laboratories and measurement systems.

4.9 Conclusions

Deliverable D2 establishes a coherent metrological framework for the characterization of instrument transformers up to 150 kHz. The work demonstrates that extending calibration activities into the supraharmonic range is technically feasible, but that measurement uncertainty increasingly becomes the limiting factor, particularly for low-amplitude harmonic components.

The deliverable confirms that both frequency-domain and time-domain performance indexes are required to fully describe wideband IT behaviour. Traditional ratio and phase errors remain fundamental, but synthetic indicators such as TFRD and THD-derived metrics provide a more comprehensive description of performance over extended frequency ranges. The study further demonstrates that realistic testing requires waveforms containing simultaneous harmonic and supraharmonic components. Frequency sweeps remain valuable because of their lower uncertainty, but multitone methods are essential for revealing non-linear effects and reproducing realistic operating conditions.

Overall, D2 provides a technical basis for future IEC standardization work and contributes practical recommendations regarding uncertainty evaluation, measurement bandwidth, acquisition-system requirements, representative test waveforms and calibration methodologies for instrument transformers operating up to 150 kHz.

5 Deliverable D3

5.1 Introduction

Deliverable D3 provides practical guidance on the generation of medium-voltage AC and DC waveforms with superimposed harmonic and supraharmonic components up to 150 kHz. The work addresses one of the key challenges identified within the ADMIT project: the absence of generation systems capable of reproducing realistic high-voltage disturbances representative of modern converter-dominated power networks [14].

The objective of the work was to establish generation architectures suitable for the characterization of voltage transformers and other voltage-dependent equipment under realistic operating conditions. The developed systems are capable of generating AC voltages up to 36 kV, DC voltages up to 50 kV, superimposed harmonic and supraharmonic components between 9 kHz and 150 kHz, and transient oscillatory waveforms representative of disturbances observed in actual networks. The deliverable consolidates several complementary solutions developed by different project partners and provides practical guidance on their implementation, performance and limitations.

5.2 Metrological Motivation

The increasing penetration of power-electronic converters, renewable generation, EV charging infrastructure and other switching devices has introduced disturbances extending well beyond the traditional harmonic range. While these phenomena are becoming increasingly relevant for power-quality measurements and instrument-transformer performance, most existing high-voltage generation facilities remain limited to frequencies below 9 kHz. Consequently, realistic testing of voltage transformers in the supraharmonic range requires dedicated generation systems capable of reproducing rated AC or DC operating conditions together with controlled high-frequency disturbances and transient events. The generation infrastructures developed within ADMIT were specifically designed to address this gap and provide the basis for future calibration services and standardized testing procedures.

5.3 Parallel-Connected AC Voltage Generation

One of the architectures investigated within the project is based on two generators operating in parallel. In this configuration, the power-frequency component and the high-frequency components are generated independently and subsequently combined at the output. This approach allows the generation of realistic composite waveforms while maintaining independent control of the fundamental and supraharmonic components. The architecture developed at LNE demonstrated that parallel operation offers a high degree of flexibility. Through software-based waveform synthesis, arbitrary combinations of single-tone, multitone and broadband harmonic signals can be generated and superimposed on the rated 50 Hz voltage. Dedicated blocking networks were introduced to minimize interaction between the low-frequency and high-frequency generation paths and to protect the associated amplifiers and transformers.

Experimental validation showed that interactions between the two generators remain limited throughout the investigated frequency range. The influence of the high-frequency source on the fundamental component remained below 0.1 %, while the effect of the power-frequency generator on the high-frequency components remained moderate even at the highest frequencies. These results demonstrate that the architecture is capable of generating realistic wideband waveforms with good stability and repeatability. A further advantage is the scalability of the concept. By adapting the amplifiers and coupling elements, the same approach can potentially be extended beyond 150 kHz toward the frequency ranges covered by the WB4 accuracy class.

5.4 Series-Connected AC Voltage Generation

A second approach, developed at the University of Campania, relies on the series connection of independently generated low-frequency and high-frequency components. In this architecture, the fundamental component is generated through a conventional step-up transformer, while the supraharmonic components are injected through a dedicated high-frequency path. The principal advantage of this configuration is its simplicity and modularity. Unlike the parallel solution, however, the frequency response of the step-up transformer becomes a dominant factor because the transformer directly affects the generated high-frequency waveform.

To address this issue, the project developed a compensation methodology based on the characterization of the complete generation chain. Measured transfer functions of the waveform generators, amplifiers and transformers were used to pre-distort the generated waveform and compensate for the frequency-dependent behaviour of the system. The experimental results demonstrated that generation errors below approximately 0.6 % can be achieved across the frequency range from 10 kHz to 150 kHz. At the same time, the study highlighted the strong influence of environmental and operating conditions. Both transformer temperature and burden were found to significantly affect the transfer function and therefore the accuracy of the generated waveform. As a result, temperature monitoring and burden characterization were identified as essential requirements whenever this architecture is employed.

5.5 Simplified Single-Transformer Approach

A further development carried out at INRIM investigated a simplified generation architecture intended primarily for industrial laboratories. The approach relies on a single wideband amplifier, a commercial step-up transformer and software-based compensation techniques. Compared with dual-generator systems, this solution significantly reduces hardware complexity and cost. The trade-off is a greater dependence on the characterization of the transformer frequency response and on the effectiveness of the compensation algorithms.

The experimental results confirmed that satisfactory performance up to 150 kHz can be achieved, provided that the operating conditions remain controlled and the compensation functions are regularly updated. The deliverable therefore identifies this architecture as particularly attractive for routine industrial applications where simplicity and ease of implementation are important considerations.

5.6 DC Voltage Generation with Superimposed Supraharmonics

The project also addressed the generation of high-frequency disturbances superimposed on high-voltage DC waveforms. Initial investigations performed at FFII considered a series-connected architecture combining a 50 kV DC source with a high-frequency amplifier and a dedicated high-frequency voltage transformer.

The experimental work demonstrated that the presence of the DC component has only a limited influence on the generation of the high-frequency signal, provided that transformer saturation effects are properly controlled. These results enabled the development of an improved architecture in which the high-frequency injection path was relocated to ground potential. This modification substantially simplified insulation requirements because the high-frequency transformer no longer needed to withstand the full DC voltage. The resulting system proved capable of generating approximately 1 kV RMS of harmonic content superimposed on 50 kV DC across the entire frequency range from 9 kHz to 150 kHz. The deliverable identifies this solution as one of the most practical outcomes of the project due to its simplicity, scalability and reduced insulation constraints.

5.7 Transient Voltage Generation

In addition to stationary harmonic and supraharmonic waveforms, D3 investigated the generation of transient disturbances representative of oscillatory overvoltages observed in practical networks. The developed transient generator is based on a resonant RLC discharge circuit. By charging a capacitor and rapidly discharging it through a suitable inductive network, damped oscillatory voltages can be generated with frequencies ranging from approximately 9 kHz to 150 kHz. Different transformer configurations were used to optimize performance in the lower, intermediate and upper portions of the frequency range.

Experimental validation demonstrated the ability to generate repeatable damped oscillatory voltages with peak amplitudes of approximately 3 kV throughout the entire target frequency interval. These results confirm that transient testing can be integrated into future wideband characterization procedures, extending the assessment beyond stationary harmonic conditions and enabling the investigation of realistic resonance and overvoltage phenomena.

5.8 Conclusions

Deliverable D3 demonstrates that the generation of realistic medium-voltage waveforms containing harmonic, supraharmonic and transient components up to 150 kHz is technically feasible through a range of complementary approaches. The work shows that parallel-connected architectures provide the highest flexibility and the lowest interaction between frequency components, while series-connected solutions offer simpler implementation at the expense of requiring compensation for transformer frequency response.

Simplified single-transformer systems appear particularly suitable for industrial laboratories, whereas the ground-referenced DC injection architecture provides an effective solution for high-voltage DC applications. Finally, transient RLC-based generators enable the reproduction of damped oscillatory disturbances representative of real network events. Together, these developments provide a comprehensive generation infrastructure for the characterization of voltage transformers under realistic wideband conditions. They constitute an important technical basis for future calibration services, laboratory validation activities and future IEC standardization work related to instrument-transformer testing in the supraharmonic range.

6 Deliverable D4

6.1 Introduction

Deliverable D4 provides practical guidance on the generation of high-current AC and DC waveforms with superimposed harmonic and supraharmonic components up to 150 kHz. The work addresses the development, validation and characterization of generation systems intended for the calibration and testing of current transformers and other current-dependent devices under realistic power-quality conditions.

The activity directly supports the objectives of the ADMIT project, which aims to extend traceable calibration capabilities into the supraharmonic range [1]. The deliverable focuses on the generation of currents up to 2 kA with controlled spectral content representative of disturbances encountered in modern medium-voltage networks affected by converter-based technologies and switching devices [14]. To achieve this objective, several complementary generation architectures were developed and validated by different project partners, covering both continuous-wave and transient operating conditions.

6.2 Metrological Motivation

The increasing deployment of renewable-energy converters, EV charging infrastructure and power-electronic equipment has introduced current disturbances extending well beyond the traditional harmonic range [15]. While significant progress has been achieved in the characterization of instrument transformers up to several kilohertz through projects such as EMPIR IT4PQ [16], traceable generation of high-current waveforms above 9 kHz remains largely unavailable. The ability to reproduce realistic current waveforms containing both the rated power-frequency component and superimposed disturbances up to 150 kHz is essential for the characterization of current transformers under actual operating conditions. Such generation capabilities are also necessary for the future development of calibration services, power-quality assessments and standardized test procedures.

6.3 Parallel-Separated Current Generation Architectures

The principal generation concept investigated within the project is based on the physical separation of the low-frequency and high-frequency current paths. In this architecture, one source generates the power-frequency current and its low-order harmonics, while a second source independently generates the supraharmonic components. Both currents pass simultaneously through the current transformer under test. This approach was adopted by several partners because it minimizes interaction between the low-frequency and high-frequency generation paths while maintaining independent control of the generated components.

The RISE implementation demonstrated the feasibility of generating currents up to 2 kA at power frequency while simultaneously producing supraharmonic components from 2 kHz to 150 kHz. The architecture combines a high-current power-frequency source with a dedicated broadband transconductance amplifier for the high-frequency content. Particular attention was devoted to synchronized acquisition and FFT processing, allowing accurate characterization of the generated waveforms. Experimental validation using a Pearson 301X current sensor showed ratio errors below approximately 0.08 % throughout the supraharmonic range, while phase errors remained below 3 %.

The VSL system follows a similar philosophy, combining a high-current generation path with a broadband high-frequency path. A significant aspect of this work was the development of compensation techniques intended to reduce the influence of transformer magnetization and impedance variations at high frequencies. The experimental results confirmed excellent performance over a broad frequency range, although increasing deviations were observed above several kilohertz due to the bandwidth limitations of the compensation electronics employed in the reference current transformers [17], [18].

A third implementation developed by VTT combines a multitone generation system with a separate high-current source. This approach allows the simultaneous generation of several frequency components while maintaining coherent sampling and avoiding spectral leakage. The resulting system demonstrated signal-to-noise ratios of approximately 75 dB and was shown to be suitable for characterization up to 100 kHz while remaining compatible with high-current operation up to several kiloamperes.

Taken together, these developments demonstrate that physically separated generation paths constitute a practical and effective solution for reproducing realistic current waveforms containing both rated currents and supraharmonic disturbances.

6.4 Parallel-Grounded Generation Architectures

A second generation philosophy was investigated by UniCampania and INRIM. In this case, the low-frequency and high-frequency generators operate in parallel within a common electrical branch rather than through physically separated conductors. The approach combines a high-current power-frequency source and a lower-power high-frequency generator through suitable blocking elements and reference measurement systems. The main objective was to evaluate the extent to which both generators interact and how this interaction affects the generated waveform.

Experimental investigations showed that interactions remain limited at lower frequencies but become increasingly significant as frequency increases. When two transconductance amplifiers were operated simultaneously, generation errors remained below approximately 1 % up to about 80 kHz but increased to approximately 4.5 % at 150 kHz. These deviations were attributed to coupling mechanisms between the generators and to amplification of high-frequency components within the low-frequency generation path.

Alternative configurations employing a step-up current transformer instead of a transconductance amplifier demonstrated that the interaction strongly depends on transformer inductance and turns ratio. The results clearly indicate that inductance and impedance design are key parameters when implementing parallel-grounded architectures and must be carefully considered if such approaches are used for standardized testing.

6.5 Transient Current Generation

In addition to stationary waveforms, the project investigated the generation of transient current disturbances representative of realistic oscillatory events occurring in power systems. Initial studies considered a series-connected architecture. However, this solution proved unsuitable because the large 50 Hz current caused saturation of the high-frequency transformer and significantly increased the inductance of the generation loop. As a result, the achievable transient current remained well below the project requirements and the concept was abandoned.

The final solution adopted a parallel configuration combining a conventional high-current source with a resonant RLC transient generator. In this architecture, capacitor banks are discharged through resonant inductive networks and high-frequency injection transformers to generate damped oscillatory currents. Experimental characterization demonstrated that the two current paths remain largely independent. More than 99.6 % of the 50 Hz current remained confined to the intended low-frequency branch, while approximately 80 % of the transient current remained within the high-frequency branch. This confirms the effectiveness of the architecture in preserving the characteristics of both generated components.

The system successfully generated power-frequency currents up to 2 kA, superimposed damped oscillatory currents with peak values approaching 500 A, and frequencies between approximately 9 kHz and 160 kHz.

The study also highlighted the importance of the injection instant relative to the fundamental waveform. Transformer saturation effects become significantly more pronounced when the transient is injected near the peak of the 50 Hz current, whereas operation close to the current zero crossing produces substantially better results.

6.6 Conclusions

Deliverable D4 demonstrates that realistic generation of high-current waveforms containing harmonic, supraharmmonic and transient components up to 150 kHz is technically feasible using a range of complementary architectures. The work shows that architectures based on physically separated low-frequency and high-frequency current paths provide the best performance for continuous-wave generation and offer the greatest flexibility for current-transformer characterization. Broadband transconductance amplifiers, synchronized acquisition systems, wideband shunts and coherent FFT processing were identified as essential elements for achieving low uncertainty and maintaining waveform fidelity.

The investigations also demonstrated that coupling effects become increasingly relevant above approximately 80 kHz and that inductance and impedance design play a decisive role in the performance of wideband current generation systems. For transient generation, dedicated compensation and isolation techniques are required to avoid saturation phenomena and maintain repeatable operation.

Overall, the deliverable provides practical guidance for the implementation of current-generation systems suitable for instrument-transformer characterization up to 150 kHz. These developments constitute an important step toward future traceable calibration infrastructures and provide valuable technical input for future IEC standardization activities related to wideband current transformers and power-quality measurements.

7 Deliverable D5

7.1 Introduction

Deliverable D5 presents the validation of the reference voltage measurement systems developed within the ADMIT project for the characterization and calibration of medium-voltage instrument transformers under realistic power-quality conditions. The objective of the work was to extend traceable voltage measurements beyond the traditional power-frequency range and into the supraharmic interval up to 150 kHz, where converter-based technologies increasingly introduce disturbances that challenge existing metrological infrastructures [16].

The deliverable focuses on the validation of complete reference measurement chains, including voltage dividers, reference sensors, comparator systems, digitizers, traceability routes and uncertainty evaluation procedures. The systems developed by the project partners collectively provide traceable measurement capabilities covering AC voltages up to 36 kV, DC voltages up to 50 kV and harmonic or supraharmic components up to at least 150 kHz. The work demonstrates that the implementation of the new wideband accuracy classes introduced in IEC 61869 requires dedicated measurement architectures capable of resolving harmonic components that are often several orders of magnitude smaller than the fundamental quantity.

7.2 Measurement Challenges in the Supraharmic Range

One of the principal challenges addressed in D5 is the simultaneous measurement of large AC or DC voltages together with very small harmonic and supraharmic components. In practice, harmonic amplitudes may represent only a few hundredths of a percent of the nominal voltage, requiring measurement systems with very high dynamic range, low noise and well-characterized frequency response.

The deliverable highlights that existing reference systems available at many National Metrology Institutes remain largely limited to frequencies below 9 kHz, while the increasing presence of converter-based equipment in modern power systems is creating a growing need for traceable measurements up to at least 150 kHz. Extending traceability into this frequency range therefore requires not only wideband voltage dividers but also dedicated signal-conditioning stages, synchronized acquisition systems and rigorous uncertainty analysis.

7.3 Development of Wideband Reference Voltage Systems

Several complementary approaches were investigated within the project to address different calibration and monitoring needs. The system developed by LNE represents one of the most comprehensive solutions. Its architecture is based on a specially designed high-voltage RC divider feeding two parallel measurement paths. One path is optimized for the measurement of the fundamental component and relatively strong harmonics, while the second path incorporates a high-pass filtering strategy that suppresses the fundamental and enhances sensitivity to very low-level harmonic components. This dual-path approach directly addresses one of the most challenging aspects of wideband voltage measurements: the simultaneous presence of a large fundamental component and very small supraharmic signals.

A dedicated RC divider was specifically developed because existing commercial dividers generally did not provide the required combination of bandwidth, stability and sensitivity. The resulting system demonstrated expanded uncertainties below 0.5 % for harmonic components above 1 mV while maintaining excellent performance at power frequency. The work also showed that FFT-based processing provides significantly better performance than conventional RMS-based approaches when very small harmonic components must be resolved.

The RISE contribution focused on the development of the RCR36 divider, extending previous work performed within the HVcom2 project. The system combines resistive and capacitive branches to achieve a nearly flat frequency response up to and beyond 150 kHz. In addition, active band-pass amplification techniques were introduced to enhance the sensitivity of the measurement chain to supraharmic components. The resulting uncertainty levels, approximately 0.06 % in amplitude and 0.02 mrad in phase up to 150 kHz, demonstrate the suitability of the architecture for both calibration and network-monitoring applications.

The VTT system adopts a different philosophy based on multitone generation and coherent acquisition. By ensuring that all generated frequency components fall exactly within FFT bins, spectral leakage is eliminated and highly accurate amplitude and phase measurements can be performed. The validated system

demonstrated scale-factor uncertainties below 0.1 % and phase uncertainties below 20 mrad for voltages extending to 100 kV and frequencies beyond 100 kHz.

7.4 Validation of Practical and Industrial Solutions

A further objective of the project was to investigate whether commercially available instrumentation can provide useful traceable capabilities in the supraharmic range.

The INRIM contribution demonstrated that carefully characterized commercial voltage dividers and acquisition systems can achieve acceptable performance up to 150 kHz. Although the resulting uncertainties are larger than those achieved with dedicated metrological systems, they remain sufficiently low for many calibration and research activities. This result is particularly relevant for industrial laboratories, where the adoption of highly specialized reference systems may not always be practical.

The FFII contribution focused on the characterization of a wideband divider system under realistic operating conditions. In addition to frequency response, the study investigated practical influence quantities such as self-heating, conductor length and the proximity of grounded structures. The results showed that conductor length becomes a significant contributor to uncertainty at high frequencies, while thermal effects and nearby grounded structures have negligible influence. These findings highlight the importance of installation conditions and demonstrate that practical aspects can become comparable to purely metrological effects when operating above several tens of kilohertz.

7.5 Dedicated High-Frequency Reference Devices

The University of Campania developed a dedicated High-Frequency Reference Device (HFRD) specifically intended for the characterization of voltage transformers in the presence of superimposed harmonic and supraharmic components [\[19\]](#).

Unlike conventional voltage dividers, the HFRD behaves essentially as a band-pass structure. The device strongly attenuates the 50 Hz component while preserving the frequency range between 9 kHz and 150 kHz. This approach significantly reduces the dynamic-range requirements imposed on the acquisition system and enables more accurate measurement of low-amplitude disturbances.

Extensive characterization demonstrated good stability with respect to frequency, voltage level and parasitic effects. The device was subsequently applied to the characterization of commercial voltage transformers. The results confirmed that low-power voltage transformers generally exhibit more favourable wideband behaviour than conventional inductive voltage transformers, whose resonances increasingly influence performance as frequency rises.

7.6 Traceability and Uncertainty Evaluation

A common outcome of all investigated systems is the central role of uncertainty evaluation. The deliverable demonstrates that accurate wideband calibration requires not only suitable reference dividers but also complete traceability chains extending from the divider itself through the signal-conditioning stages, acquisition system and data-processing algorithms.

A recurring conclusion throughout the project is that uncertainty increasingly depends on frequency-dependent effects rather than on the nominal accuracy of the divider alone. The dominant contributors become the frequency response of the divider, digitizer performance, impedance matching, installation conditions and the ability to resolve very small harmonic amplitudes in the presence of a much larger fundamental signal.

The work therefore provides practical examples of uncertainty evaluation methodologies that can be applied to future wideband calibration systems and can support future revisions of IEC 61869.

7.7 Conclusions

Deliverable D5 establishes a comprehensive metrological framework for traceable voltage measurements up to 150 kHz and demonstrates that several complementary architectures can successfully address different calibration and monitoring requirements. The work confirms that accurate wideband characterization of instrument transformers requires dedicated reference systems specifically designed for operation in the supraharmic range. While different approaches were investigated, a common conclusion is that high-

frequency measurements demand carefully characterized voltage dividers, synchronized acquisition systems, appropriate signal conditioning and rigorous uncertainty analysis.

The various systems developed within the project demonstrate different strengths. The LNE architecture provides a particularly effective solution for the detection of very small harmonic components, while RISE and VTT emphasize wideband monitoring and calibration capabilities. INRIM demonstrates the feasibility of industrially practical solutions based on commercial instrumentation, FFII highlights the importance of installation effects, and UniCampania introduces a dedicated high-frequency reference device specifically optimized for wideband voltage-transformer characterization. Collectively, these developments extend traceable voltage measurement capabilities into the supraharmonic range and provide the experimental and metrological foundation required for future calibration services and for the implementation of the IEC 61869 wideband accuracy classes.

8 Deliverable D6

8.1 Introduction

Deliverable D6 presents the validation of the reference current measurement systems developed within Task 3.2 of the ADMIT project for the traceable characterization of current transformers (CTs) up to 2 kA and frequencies extending to 150 kHz. The objective is to establish complete measurement chains capable of supporting wideband CT calibration and conformity assessment under realistic power-quality conditions, including harmonics and supraharmonics generated by modern power-electronic systems [14].

The work focuses on the characterization of reference sensors, comparator systems, acquisition chains, traceability routes and uncertainty budgets. The developed systems are intended to provide uncertainty levels significantly lower than the accuracy limits of the CTs under test and to support future calibration services and standardization activities within IEC TC38. Deliverable D6 complements Deliverable D4, which addressed current generation systems, by validating the corresponding reference measurement infrastructures.

8.2 Metrological Context

The increasing penetration of converter-based generation, renewable energy sources and power-electronic loads has significantly extended the frequency range relevant for current measurements. As a result, the characterization of current transformers can no longer be limited to the traditional 50/60 Hz range but must also address harmonic and supraharmonic components extending to at least 150 kHz [14].

To address this need, ADMIT developed several complementary reference measurement systems at different NMIs and research institutes. Although the technical implementations differ, all systems rely on the same fundamental metrological principle: establishing traceability to the SI through calibrated current shunts, reference current transformers, precision voltage measurements and synchronized acquisition systems.

8.3 VSL Reference Measurement System

The VSL system was developed for the traceable characterization of window-type CTs from 50 Hz up to 150 kHz. Its measurement principle is based on a ratio-comparison method in which the device under test and a reference CT simultaneously measure the same primary current. The ratio error and phase displacement of the DUT are then obtained from the complex ratio of the measured secondary currents [17].

The architecture employs separate primary conductors for the power-frequency current and the superimposed high-frequency components, following the generation philosophy described in D4. On the measurement side, a Yokogawa WT5000 broadband power analyzer is used as a precision sampling comparator. A key feature of the system is the use of NRC electronically compensated current transformers as reference CTs [20]. These devices exhibit uncertainties below 20 ppm and 20 μ rad up to approximately 5 kHz. Beyond this frequency, however, the finite bandwidth of the internal compensation electronics becomes increasingly visible and produces measurable deviations. The work shows that these effects become significant above approximately 10 kHz and therefore need to be explicitly included in the uncertainty analysis.

Traceability is achieved through calibrated broadband current shunts and voltage standards. The most accurate configuration achieves uncertainties of only a few parts in 10^4 and a few tenths of a milliradian at 150 kHz [18]. A simplified primary-secondary measurement method is also available, although with somewhat larger uncertainties, typically in the range of a few parts in 10^3 .

8.4 METAS Reference Measurement System

The METAS system follows a more direct comparison approach, where the primary current measured by calibrated shunts is compared with the secondary current delivered by the CT under test. The ratio error is determined from the difference between the measured transformation ratio and the nominal ratio.

Current generation is based on a function generator and a transconductance amplifier, while multi-turn configurations are used to increase the effective primary current without requiring excessively large amplifier currents. Traceability is established through calibrated shunts and calibrated analyzer channels linked to SI references.

The achieved uncertainties are typically on the order of a few hundred ppm in amplitude and a few tenths of a milliradian in phase. The study highlights that, at high frequencies, the dominant uncertainty contributions

increasingly arise from analyzer performance and parasitic effects associated with cabling and connections rather than from the reference shunts themselves.

8.5 FFII Reference Measurement System

The FFII system was developed as a practical wideband solution covering the frequency range from 50 Hz to 150 kHz. The setup combines a conventional reference transformer for power-frequency operation with a Fluke i800s wideband current clamp for measurements in the supraharmmonic interval.

The measurement chain employs a Yokogawa WT5000 power analyzer together with dedicated waveform-processing algorithms based on signal correlation and sinusoidal fitting techniques. These methods allow harmonic amplitudes and phases to be extracted while suppressing background noise.

Traceability is established through calibration of the current clamp against a TRANSMILLE AC/DC coaxial shunt whose frequency dependence has been characterized with ppm-level accuracy. The resulting expanded uncertainty is approximately 0.39 % at 9 kHz and increases to around 2.7 % at 150 kHz, while phase uncertainties remain close to 0.9 crad throughout the investigated frequency range. Although these uncertainty levels are higher than those achieved by dedicated NMI systems, they remain suitable for a wide range of practical applications.

8.6 RISE Reference Measurement System

The RISE system is based on the same generation infrastructure described in Deliverable D4, combining high-current power-frequency generation with independent supraharmmonic current injection up to 150 kHz.

The reference measurement chain employs HITEC zero-flux current transformers for the fundamental and low-order harmonics, a RISE CS2D broadband current shunt for supraharmmonic measurements, and a PXIe-6396 simultaneous-sampling digitizer. Sampling rates above 1 MS/s are used together with FFT-based processing to preserve phase accuracy and avoid spectral leakage.

Experimental characterization of a Pearson 301X current sensor confirmed good performance in the supraharmmonic range, with ratio errors below 0.08 % and phase errors below 3 %. In addition, a Rogowski coil (PEM CWT15) was identified as a promising candidate for substation monitoring applications.

Traceability is established through calibrated broadband shunts, HITEC zero-flux transformers and calibration of the digitizer against a Fluke 5700A calibrator. The resulting expanded uncertainties remain below ± 0.02 % and 1 mrad below 1 kHz, and below ± 0.16 % and 2.5 mrad at 150 kHz.

8.7 VTT Reference Measurement System

The VTT contribution adopts a multitone measurement philosophy. Multiple frequency components are generated simultaneously and measured using coherent acquisition so that every frequency component falls exactly into a dedicated FFT bin. This eliminates spectral leakage and allows efficient characterization of wideband sensors and shunts.

The measurement system combines waveform generators, transconductance amplifiers, wideband reference shunts and synchronized digitizers. A separate high-current source capable of generating up to 8 kA at power frequency can be combined with the multitone generator to reproduce realistic operating conditions.

Traceability is based on a family of wideband shunts whose AC/DC ratios have been characterized with ppm-level accuracy throughout the frequency range. The resulting uncertainties remain below 0.1 % for ratio measurements and below 2 crad for phase measurements up to 150 kHz, demonstrating the effectiveness of coherent multitone techniques for CT characterization.

8.8 Traceability and Uncertainty Framework

Although the architectures developed by the different partners differ significantly, D6 identifies a common traceability framework. All systems ultimately rely on calibrated electrical quantities such as resistance, voltage, current, time and frequency. Reference elements include electronically compensated CTs, zero-flux transformers, broadband shunts, Rogowski sensors, Hall-effect devices and current clamps, selected according to the required current range, bandwidth and uncertainty target.

Similarly, comparator functionality is realized through broadband power analyzers, synchronized digitizers or dedicated multitone acquisition systems. A major achievement of Task 3.2 is the successful extension of these comparator concepts into the supraharmonic range while maintaining traceable amplitude and phase measurements.

The report emphasizes that, above approximately 10 kHz, uncertainty increasingly depends on setup-related effects rather than on the intrinsic performance of the reference sensor. Cable and connector effects, parasitic inductances and capacitances, grounding arrangements, bandwidth limitations and signal-processing algorithms become dominant contributors and must therefore be explicitly characterized.

The uncertainty analysis follows the principles of the GUM and combines contributions associated with reference sensor calibration, acquisition channel calibration, frequency-dependent effects, signal processing, repeatability and long-term stability. Representative uncertainty budgets demonstrate that state-of-the-art systems can achieve combined standard uncertainties of approximately 150–200 ppm in amplitude and 0.2–0.3 mrad in phase, corresponding to expanded uncertainties of about 300–400 ppm and 0.4–0.6 mrad respectively.

8.9 Conclusions

Deliverable D6 establishes the metrological foundation for traceable current-transformer characterization up to 2 kA and 150 kHz. The work demonstrates that several complementary approaches can successfully extend CT calibration into the supraharmonic range, provided that frequency-dependent effects are properly characterized and included in the uncertainty budget.

The study confirms that reference CTs remain attractive for high-current applications, while broadband shunts provide excellent traceability at high frequencies. It also demonstrates that synchronized sampling analyzers and digitizers can successfully operate as wideband comparators and that uncertainty increasingly depends on setup-related effects rather than on the reference sensors themselves.

Among the investigated systems, VSL and METAS achieve the lowest uncertainty levels, while RISE and VTT provide highly versatile architectures suitable for both calibration and monitoring applications. FFII demonstrates that simpler and more practical wideband solutions can also provide useful capabilities for industrial environments.

Collectively, these developments establish a robust metrological basis for future calibration services, conformity assessment of wideband current transformers and future IEC standardization activities in the field of power-quality measurements up to 150 kHz.

9 Deliverable D7

9.1 Introduction

Deliverable D7 represents the final synthesis of the ADMIT project and serves as the vehicle for transferring the project outcomes to IEC/CENELEC TC38 for consideration in future revisions and developments of the IEC 61869 family of standards. Rather than introducing new experimental work, the deliverable consolidates the results obtained throughout the project and transforms them into a coherent set of technical recommendations concerning the characterization of instrument transformers up to 150 kHz.

The document brings together the outcomes of all technical work packages, including the characterization of disturbances in medium-voltage networks, the definition of accuracy and uncertainty requirements for instrument transformers, the development of voltage and current generation systems, the validation of reference measurement systems, and the establishment of traceability chains, uncertainty budgets, test procedures and performance indexes. Its primary purpose is to provide standardization bodies with validated technical evidence capable of supporting future developments in the field of wideband instrument transformers.

9.2 Standardization Context and Existing Gaps

The deliverable begins by highlighting the growing relevance of high-frequency distortion and supraharmonics in modern power systems. The increasing deployment of photovoltaic generation, wind-power installations, EV charging infrastructure and converter-based technologies has resulted in the widespread presence of disturbances above 9 kHz, extending well into the 150 kHz region [2].

Although IEC 61869-1 Edition 2 introduced the wideband accuracy classes WB0 to WB4, extending the concept of accuracy up to 500 kHz, the standard currently provides only performance limits and does not specify how compliance should be verified. In particular, harmonized guidance remains absent with respect to representative test waveforms, harmonic amplitudes, generation systems, reference measurement systems, uncertainty evaluation procedures and the treatment of environmental influence quantities.

As a consequence, different laboratories may currently adopt different methodologies, potentially leading to non-comparable results. The deliverable identifies this lack of harmonized testing procedures as the principal standardization gap addressed by ADMIT.

9.3 Characterization of Real-World Disturbances

A central outcome of the project concerns the characterization of realistic disturbances occurring in the frequency range between 9 kHz and 150 kHz. Drawing upon literature reviews, numerical simulations and field measurements, the project established a consistent picture of the supraharmonic environment present in modern medium-voltage networks.

The analysis confirmed that the dominant sources of supraharmonic emissions are converter-based technologies such as photovoltaic systems and EV chargers [2]. The most significant emissions are generally concentrated around switching frequencies between approximately 10 kHz and 50 kHz, particularly around 10 kHz and 12–16 kHz, although resonances may generate components extending towards 100–150 kHz. Field measurements carried out in medium-voltage networks showed that supraharmonic voltages are typically limited to a few tens of volts, corresponding to only a small fraction of the nominal system voltage. Similarly, current disturbances generally remain below 1 A. However, the simulations and measurements also demonstrated that network resonances can locally amplify disturbances and significantly modify their propagation. Transformer parasitic capacitances, cable lengths and loading conditions were identified as particularly influential parameters governing wideband behaviour.

These findings provide an important basis for the definition of representative test conditions and realistic performance requirements.

9.4 Accuracy and Uncertainty Requirements

The deliverable consolidates the uncertainty analyses developed in D1 and D2 and translates them into practical requirements for instrument-transformer characterization.

The work confirms that metrological traceability relies on calibration chains originating from National Metrology Institutes and that conformity assessment requires an adequate Test Uncertainty Ratio. A TUR greater than three was identified as the minimum requirement for reliable verification of compliance.

The analysis demonstrates that uncertainty increases significantly with frequency and becomes increasingly dependent on the amplitude of the harmonic component being measured. In particular, when harmonic outputs fall into the millivolt or milliampere range, the uncertainty is often dominated by the performance of the measurement system rather than by the instrument transformer itself.

The deliverable therefore recommends that future standards consider not only the performance of the transformer under test but also the practical limitations of the measurement systems used for its characterization. This issue becomes particularly relevant when attempting to verify compliance with wideband accuracy classes at very low signal levels.

9.5 Recommended Test Conditions

Based on the combined evidence from literature reviews, simulations and measurement campaigns, the project proposes a harmonized set of test conditions intended to reproduce realistic operating environments.

The recommended approach is to test instrument transformers with harmonic and supraharmonic amplitudes corresponding to approximately 1–5 % of the nominal quantity. For voltage transformers, this implies several hundred volts of superimposed high-frequency content on medium-voltage fundamentals, while for current transformers it corresponds to several amperes of superimposed high-frequency current.

The analysis also indicates that lower-frequency supraharmonics generally exhibit larger amplitudes and that frequencies below approximately 50 kHz deserve particular attention because they contain the dominant emissions associated with most converter technologies. These recommendations are intended to support the development of future harmonized test procedures.

9.6 Performance Indexes for Wideband Characterization

A further contribution of the project concerns the definition of performance indexes suitable for characterizing instrument transformers beyond the traditional ratio and phase errors.

The deliverable recommends extending the characterization framework to include indicators such as harmonic transfer functions, Total Frequency Response Deviation (TFRD), Total Vector Error (TVE) and THD-derived wideband metrics. These indicators provide a more comprehensive description of transformer behaviour across extended frequency ranges and facilitate comparison between different technologies.

The project also recommends the use of time-domain performance indicators, including waveform-error norms and correlation-based metrics, particularly for transient and protection-oriented applications. The overall conclusion is that neither frequency-domain nor time-domain indicators alone are sufficient to fully characterize wideband behaviour and that future standards should consider both perspectives.

9.7 Proposed Test Waveforms

The deliverable recommends a family of representative test waveforms derived from the disturbance characteristics identified throughout the project.

For frequency-domain testing, the preferred approach is the use of composite waveforms combining the fundamental component with harmonic and supraharmonic tones. Particular emphasis is placed on switching frequencies around 8 kHz, 10 kHz and 16 kHz, which are representative of many converter-based technologies and whose harmonics may remain significant up to approximately 50 kHz.

For transient testing, the project recommends the use of tapered sinc waveforms, oscillatory transients and surge-type signals capable of exciting a broad frequency range. These waveforms were successfully employed during the round-robin activities conducted within WP2 and WP3 and are considered representative of realistic operating conditions.

The deliverable recommends that future standards adopt similar waveform families in order to ensure consistency between laboratories and realistic assessment of wideband performance.

9.8 Generation and Measurement Infrastructures

The document also consolidates the generation and measurement infrastructures developed throughout the project.

For voltage applications, the validated solutions include parallel-connected generators, series-connected generators, transformer-based architectures and transient generation systems capable of producing realistic waveforms up to 36 kV and 150 kHz. For current applications, the project demonstrated dual-source architectures, parallel-generation concepts, multitone systems and transient generators capable of producing currents up to 2 kA with superimposed high-frequency components.

The corresponding reference measurement systems developed by LNE, RISE, VTT, INRIM, FFII, UniCampania, VSL and METAS collectively establish traceable measurement capabilities extending into the supraharmonic range. Together, these infrastructures provide the metrological foundation necessary for future calibration services and conformity assessment activities.

9.9 Recommendations for IEC/CENELEC TC38

The central outcome of Deliverable D7 is a set of recommendations intended to support future revisions of the IEC 61869 family of standards.

The project recommends the introduction of representative test waveforms extending to at least 150 kHz, together with harmonized definitions of harmonic amplitudes, reference measurement systems and uncertainty evaluation procedures. The work further recommends expanding the characterization framework beyond conventional ratio and phase errors by introducing additional performance indexes capable of describing wideband behaviour.

Particular attention is devoted to the distinction between simplified frequency-sweep methods and multitone approaches. While frequency sweeps generally provide lower uncertainty, multitone methods more closely reproduce realistic operating conditions and reveal non-linear effects that may remain hidden under single-tone excitation. The deliverable therefore recommends that both approaches be considered in future standardization activities.

The project also recommends that future standards explicitly address environmental and operating influence quantities such as burden, temperature and electromagnetic interference, as these factors have been shown to significantly affect wideband performance.

9.10 Conclusions

Deliverable D7 serves as the formal bridge between the technical outcomes of ADMIT and future standardization activities. It demonstrates that accurate characterization of instrument transformers up to 150 kHz is technically feasible, provided that appropriate generation systems, reference measurement infrastructures, traceability chains and uncertainty evaluation procedures are available.

The project confirms that the existing IEC standards already provide the framework of wideband accuracy classes but still lack the practical methodologies required for their implementation. It also demonstrates that realistic disturbance levels can be identified and reproduced, that multitone and transient testing are essential for realistic assessment, and that uncertainty increasingly depends on acquisition systems and low-level signal measurements as frequency increases.

By consolidating the outcomes of all technical work packages into a coherent set of recommendations, Deliverable D7 provides IEC/CENELEC TC38 with a comprehensive technical basis for the future development of standards addressing instrument-transformer performance in the supraharmonic range up to 150 kHz.

10 General Conclusion

The ADMIT project has established a comprehensive technical and metrological framework for the characterization of instrument transformers operating in the extended frequency range up to 150 kHz. Through coordinated activities covering disturbance characterization, calibration methodologies, uncertainty analysis, generation systems and reference measurement infrastructures, the project has addressed many of the key challenges associated with wideband instrument-transformer assessment.

The work confirmed that supraharmmonic disturbances are now a relevant feature of modern medium-voltage networks and that existing standards do not yet provide complete methodologies for evaluating instrument-transformer performance in this frequency range. The project demonstrated that realistic testing requires the consideration of harmonic, supraharmmonic and transient phenomena, together with the influence of network resonances and practical operating conditions.

The generation systems developed within the project proved capable of reproducing realistic voltage and current waveforms up to 36 kV, 50 kV DC and 2 kA, with superimposed frequency components extending to 150 kHz. In parallel, the validated reference measurement systems established traceable voltage and current measurement capabilities with uncertainty levels suitable for calibration and conformity assessment activities.

A recurring conclusion throughout the project is that measurement uncertainty increasingly becomes the dominant limitation as frequency increases and signal amplitudes decrease. Consequently, future standardization activities should consider not only the performance of the instrument transformer itself but also the practical capabilities and limitations of the associated measurement systems.

The project also demonstrated the importance of multitone and transient testing, the usefulness of wideband performance indexes beyond traditional ratio and phase errors, and the need for harmonized procedures covering waveform generation, uncertainty evaluation and reference measurements.

The recommendations consolidated in Deliverable D7 and submitted to IEC/CENELEC TC38 provide a technical basis for future revisions of the IEC 61869 family of standards. These recommendations contribute toward the establishment of harmonized methodologies for the characterization, calibration and conformity assessment of instrument transformers in the supraharmmonic range and support the future deployment of traceable calibration services throughout Europe.

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